

**The Formation and Stability of Polybromide Derivatives
of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part V. The Bromina-
tion of some 2-Arylimino-3-aryl-4-keto-5-methyl-
tetrahydrothiazoles and their 5:5-Dimethyl
Homologues and some Remarks on the
Theory of Singlet Linkages.**

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It was assumed in earlier investigations on the bromination of diaryl- ψ -thiohydantoin (Farooq and Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 545; Chowdhury, Desai, Hunter and Solangi, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1933, 62, 853), that the keto-enol system

present in these tetrahydrothiazole derivatives takes no part in the production of the bromo-addition compounds formed in chloroform solution at low temperatures. In view of the somewhat curious results observed in the case of 2-*p*-chlorophenylimino-3-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole and its bromine analogue, however, it appeared desirable to test the validity of this assumption by an examination of the behaviour of diaryl- ψ -thiohydantoin derivatives in which one, or both of the potentially mobile hydrogen atoms of the triad system have been alkylated. The bromination of certain 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazoles (I, $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$) and their static 5:5-dimethyl analogues (I, $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$) which are readily synthesised from the sodio derivatives of the corresponding s diarylthiocarbamides and ethyl α -bromopropionate and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate respectively (*cf.* Wilson and Burns, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 870; Chowdhury, Desai, Hunter and Solangi, *loc. cit.*), was, therefore, studied.

On treatment with bromine under the usual conditions, 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I, $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$) gave rise to an ill-defined hydroperbromide of a monobromosubstitution derivative, which on reduction with sulphurous acid yielded 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I, $R_2 = R = H$; $R_1 = Br$), whose constitution follows from its synthesis from *p*-bromo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide and ethyl α -bromopropionate (*cf.* Dains, Irvin and Harrel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 613).

2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (I, $R = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) showed, however, the closest resemblance to diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin (Farooq and Hunter, *loc. cit.*) and yielded a well defined vermilion hydroperbromide of 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (II).

2-*p*-Tolylimino-3-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I, $R = R_1 = Me$; $R_2 = H$) resembled di-*p*-tolyl- ψ -thiohydantoin (Chowdhury, Desai, Hunter and Solangi, *loc. cit.*) in giving rise to a hydroperbromide which yielded 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (III) ($R = C_7H_7$; $R_1 = Me$) on reduction with sulphurous acid. The *gem*-dimethyl homologue (I, $R = R_1 = R_2 = Me$) behaved similarly on treatment with bromine, and gave rise to an indefinite hydroperbromide of 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole.

In contrast to 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole, however, 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I, $R = R_1 = Br$; $R_2 = H$) also underwent nuclear substitution by bromine in the 3-aryl substituent yielding a hydrotribromide of a tribromodiphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin, whose constitution (III, $R = C_6H_4Br$; $R_1 = Br$) was established by synthesis from *s*-*p*-bromophenyl-*o*-*p*-dibromophenylthiocarbamide and ethyl α -bromopropionate. The 5:5-dimethyl homologue (I, $R = R_1 = Br$; $R_2 = Me$) behaved similarly, and this difference in behaviour from

2-*p*-bromophenylimino-8-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole may be attributed to the "electron source" properties of the methyl group and to the more sparing solubility of the tribromide of the latter ψ -thiohydantoin which is responsible for its early removal from the sphere of the reaction.

On the whole, the 5-methyl and 5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazoles, therefore, exhibit the closest similarity to the ψ -thiohydantoins studied in earlier investigations with regard to their behaviour towards bromine, in accordance with the original assumption that the keto-enol system in the latter plays no rôle in their bromination.

It has been suggested in earlier papers (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125; Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147; Farooq and Hunter, *loc. cit.*) that the labile bromine atoms in bromo-addition compounds of the type of benzthiazole dibromide are held to the nuclear nitrogen atom by means of singlet linkages. This suggestion was largely based on the existence of the hydrogen molecule ion $[H_2]^{\oplus}$ and the evidence of singlet linkages in pentahalides of the Fifth Group obtained from parachor measurements (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1176). It is now known, however, that the formation of molecules consists in the entry of electrons belonging to the atoms concerned into the *same group* of the electronic configuration of the molecule with resultant neutralisation of spin in accordance with Pauli's principle (Hund, *Z. Physik*, 1932, 73, 1; 74, 429). Teller's calculations (*Z. Physik*, 1930, 61, 458) show moreover that a single electron does not possess bonding power, and that the formation of the hydrogen molecule ion depends essentially on the identity of the two positive hydrogen nuclei; this case has, therefore, nothing whatever to do with ordinary chemical linkage. In the production of the so-called singlet linkage, therefore, either the electron of the semipolar single bond forms a group with one or more electrons of the second atom, in which case it is an ordinary co-valency, or it is alone in a separate group and cannot constitute a real chemical linkage (Hunter and Samuel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1180).

With regard to the evidence of singlet linkages obtained from parachor measurements of pentahalides of the Fifth Group, Sugden (*loc. cit.*) assumes that the atomic parachor of phosphorus has a constant value of 37.7 and that the discrepancy between the observed parachor of phosphorus pentachloride and that calculated on the

assumption that the molecule contains five ordinary co-valencies arises from the presence of two singlet linkages. There is, however, the obvious alternative possibility that phosphorus possesses different parachor values in the trivalent and pentavalent states. This interpretation of Sugden's observations has been suggested by Sippel (*Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 2185) since it is well known that a reverse distribution of this type is conventionally assumed in molecular refractivity, which is very closely allied to the parachor. Indeed, the essential difference between the two constants is that whereas the direct relation between molecular refractivity and atomic constants follows from the Lorentz-Lorentz formula, which establishes the fact that this quantity is a measure of the polarisation to which a molecule is subject in the electromagnetic field of the light concerned, the basis of the parachor is an empirical formula the direct relation of which to atomic constants is still unknown. If phosphorus is assumed to possess different parachor values in the trivalent and pentavalent states and Sugden's value for chlorine is accepted, and the value for doubly bound oxygen is calculated from the empirical parachor of carbon dioxide, a value of $P^v = 18.3$ may be deduced by subtraction from the observed parachor of phosphorus oxychloride (Sugden, Reed and Wilkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1185). If this value is now used to calculate the parachor of phosphorus pentachloride, a value of 284.3 is obtained which approximates closely to the observed value of 282.5 (Sugden, *loc. cit.*)

It is, therefore, clear that parachor measurements cannot provide proof of the existence of singlet linkages in such compounds, and that some other explanation must be sought for the existence of the bromo-addition compounds of heterocyclic bases of the thiazole type. It is evident that there are at least two types of bromo-addition compounds formed between benzthiazole and bromine in inert solvents. The highly unstable complexes formed in many cases are probably mere dipole associations, but the extraordinary stability of the dibromides of the 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles (Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*) suggests the presence of a pentavalent nuclear nitrogen atom, produced by the fission of the s^2 group of electrons (Hunter and Samuel, *loc. cit.*).

It is of course now clear that the hydrodibromides of the 1-amino-benzthiazoles cannot contain a $[\text{Br}_2]^\ominus$ ion involving a singlet linkage, and a specimen of 1-aminobenzthiazole hydrodibromide,

examined in Professor S. Bhatnagar's laboratory at Lahore, failed to exhibit the paramagnetism to be anticipated on the basis of an odd-electron structure. It is, therefore, probable that these hydro-

bromides are actually complexes of the type $[\text{Base}, \text{H}]_2 \overset{\ominus}{\text{Br}} \overset{\ominus}{\text{Br}} \overset{\ominus}{\text{Br}}$ (cf. Aliazam, Hunter and Noor Ahmad Khan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 708).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I) ($R = R_1 = R_2 = H$).—Ethyl α -bromopropionate (5.4 g.) was added to a solution obtained by treatment of thiocarbamilide (6.8 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) with an equivalent of sodium ethoxide in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 5-6 hours. The alcohol was removed on a water-bath and the residue was freed from sodium bromide by washing with water. On recrystallisation from alcohol it was obtained in small needles, m.p. 105°. (Found: S, 11.5. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires S, 11.3 per cent).

Bromination of (I, $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$).—A solution of the tetrahydrothiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) at 0-3°, and the mixture was kept in ice for an hour. As no crystallisation took place the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature when a vermilion coloured bromo-addition compound separated, which was collected on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide, paraffin wax and anhydrous calcium chloride. An orange coloured microcrystalline *hydroperbromide* of a monobromo-substitution derivative of the tetrahydrothiazole was thus obtained which had m.p. 149° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 58.8; Br (labile), 27.9. $C_{16}H_{13}ON_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 53.2; Br (labile), 26.6 per cent]. On treatment with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia this substance yielded 2-phenylimino-3-p-bromophenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole, which separated from alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 121-122° (Found: Br, 22.3. $C_{16}H_{13}ON_2BrS$ requires Br, 22.2 per cent). It was also synthesised from ethyl α -bromopropionate and p-bromo-s-diphenylthiocarbamide thus.—A solution of p-bromo-s-diphenylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with an equivalent of sodium ethoxide (in 5 c.c.

of absolute alcohol) and thereafter with ethyl α -bromopropionate (1 g.), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 5-6 hours. The methyltetrahydrothiazole obtained as in the previous case, separated from alcohol in needles, m.p. 122° (mixed m.p. 122°).

2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (I) ($R=R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—A solution of thiocarbanilide (4.8 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) was treated with an equivalent of sodium ethoxide (in 20 c.c. of the same solvent) and thereafter with ethyl α -isobromobutyrate (3.9 g.), and the mixture was heated for 5-6 hours. It crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: S, 11.1. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2S$ requires S, 10.8 per cent).

Bromination of (I, $R=R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—A solution of the dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) at 0–3°, and the solution was kept in ice for 2 hours when a *hydropentabromide* separated in glistening vermilion plates, m.p. 196° (decomp. with effervescence, after softening at 130°) (after drying on porous earthenware in a vacuum) [Found: Br (total), 62.2; Br (labile), 41.2. $C_{17}H_{15}ON_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br (total), 61.8; Br(labile), 41.2 per cent]. This compound lost bromine on exposure to the atmosphere after 48 hours, yielding a yellow-orange product, having the composition of a hydro-tetrabromide of the bromo-substitution derivative [Found: Br (labile), 34.5. $C_{17}H_{15}ON_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br (labile), 34.5 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid, *2-phenylimino-3-p-bromo-phenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole* was obtained, which separated from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 163°. (Found: Br, 21.1. $C_{17}H_{15}ON_2BrS$ requires Br, 21.3 per cent). It was also synthesised from ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate and *p*-bromo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide thus:—The dimethyltetrahydrothiazole prepared from *p*-bromo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide (1.5 g.) and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate (1 g.), separated from alcohol in needles which had m.p.: 163° (mixed m.p. 163°).

2-p-Tolylimino-3-p-tolyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole, (I), ($R=R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) prepared from *s*-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (5.4 g.) in the usual way, separated from alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 110° (Found: S, 10.1. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_2S$ requires S, 10.3 per cent).

Bromination of (I, $R=R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—A solution of the methyltetrahydrothiazole in chloroform (1 g. in 10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) at 0–3°, and the solution was kept at this temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and thereafter con-

centrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. An indefinite orange bromo-addition compound was obtained, m.p. 92° (decomp., after softening at 69°). [Found: Br (labile), 23·5 per cent], which was reduced with sulphurous acid in the usual way. On basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol, 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole was obtained which formed glistening plates, m.p. 157°. (Found: Br, 20·7. C₁₈H₁₇ON₂BrS requires Br, 20·5 per cent). It was also synthesised from *s*-*p*-tolyl-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide and ethyl α -bromopropionate. *s*-*p*-Tolyl-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of *o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbimide (2·6 g.) and *p*-toluidine (2·1 g.) in methyl alcohol (15 c.c.), crystallised in small plates, m.p. 168°. The methyltetrahydrothiazole obtained from this thiocarbamide (1·7 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (1 g.) in the usual way had m.p. 157° alone, and when mixed with the specimen already described.

2-*p*-Tolylimino-3-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (I), (R=R₁=R₂=Me) prepared from *s*-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (7·6 g.) and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate (5·8 g.) in the presence of an equivalent of sodium ethoxide, separated from alcohol in small crystals, m.p. 167°. (Found: S, 10·1. C₁₉H₂₀ON₂S requires S, 9·9 per cent).

Bromination of (I, R=R₁=R₂=Me).—An experiment similar to that already described in the case of 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole yielded an indefinite yellow-brown hydroperbromide, m.p. 98° (after softening at 54°). [Found: Br (labile), 25·2 per cent], which was reduced with sulphurous acid in the usual way. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole was obtained in cubes, m.p. 109° (Found: Br, 20·2. C₁₉H₁₉ON₂BrS requires Br, 19·8 per cent). It was also synthesised from *s*-*p*-tolyl-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate. The tetrahydrothiazole obtained by condensation of *s*-*p*-tolyl-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (1·7 g.) with ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate (1 g.), had m.p. 109° after recrystallisation, and was identical with the product obtained by bromination of 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*p*-tolyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole.

2-*p*-Bromophenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole (I) (R=R₁=Br; R₂=H) prepared from *s*-di-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide (10·6 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (5·4 g.) in the usual way, had m.p. 120° after recrystallisation from alcohol (Found: Br, 36·6. C₁₆H₁₂ON₂BrS requires Br, 36·4 per cent).

Bromination of (I, R=R₁=Br; R₂=H).—A solution of the tetrahydrothiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) at 0–3°, and the solution was kept at this temperature for an hour and thereafter evaporated in a vacuum at laboratory temperature. A yellow *hydrotribromide* separated which had m.p. 86° (decomp. with effervescence, after softening at 74°). [Found: Br (total), 62.9; Br (labile), 23.0. C₁₆H₁₁ON₂Br₃S, HBr (Br₂) requires Br (total), 63.15; Br (labile), 21.05 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid this bromo-addition compound yielded 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*o*-*p*-dibromophenyl-4-keto-5-methyltetrahydrothiazole, which separated from alcohol in small crystals, m.p. 90°. (Found: Br, 46.4. C₁₆H₁₁ON₂Br₃S requires Br, 46.2 per cent). It was also synthesised from *s*-*p*-bromophenyl-*o*-*p*-dibromophenylthiocarbamide. *s*-*p*-Bromophenyl-*o*-*p*-dibromophenylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of *o*-*p*-dibromophenylthiocarbimide (2.2 g.) with *p*-bromoaniline (1.3 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.), melted at 180°. (Found: Br, 51.9. C₁₃H₉N₂Br₃S requires Br, 51.6 per cent). The gummy product obtained by condensation of this thiocarbamide with ethyl α -bromopropionate in the usual way, on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate yielded identical compound with that obtained in the bromination experiment already described.

2-*p*-Bromophenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole (I) (R=R₁=Br; R₂=Me), prepared by condensation of *s*-di-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide (7 g.) in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.) containing an equivalent of sodium ethoxide with ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate (4 g.), separated from alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 165–66°. (Found: Br, 35.5. C₁₇H₁₄ON₂Br₂S requires Br, 35.2 per cent).

Bromination of (I, R=R₁=Br; R₂=Me).—The *hydrotribromide* of 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*o*-*p*-dibromophenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole obtained by bromination of the dimethyltetrahydrothiazole as in the case of the methyltetrahydrothiazole already described, formed a yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 84° (decomp., after softening at 50°). [Found: Br (total), 62.6; Br (labile), 19.4. C₁₇H₁₃ON₂Br₃S, HBr (Br₂) requires Br (total), 62.2; Br (labile), 20.7 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid, this yielded 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*o*-*p*-dibromophenyl-4-keto-5:5-dimethyltetrahydrothiazole which crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 140°. (Found: Br, 44.4. C₁₇H₁₃ON₂Br₃S requires Br, 44.9 per cent). The identical compound, obtained from the tribromothiocarbamide

(1 g.) and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate, separated from dilute alcohol in needles which melted at 140° (mixed m.p. 140°).

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Halogenation. Part X. Preparation of Mixed Halogen Derivatives of Xylenes.

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The study of the literature shows that the chloro-iodo and bromo-iodo compounds of xylenes have not been obtained before. The majority of the mixed halogen derivatives of the aromatic hydrocarbons have usually been prepared by indirect methods from the diamino-compounds by successively replacing the amino groups by the halogen atoms by the Sandmeyer's reaction. Chlorotoluenes have been successfully iodinated in this laboratory in presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid or mixture of nitro-sulphonic and fuming nitric acids. (Varma and Sahay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 293).

It has been possible to iodinate the chloro- and bromoxylenes in presence of nitrosulphonic acid mixture and very good yields of the chloro-iodo and bromo-iodo compounds have been obtained. 2-Chloro-*p*-xylene and 4-chloro-*m*-xylene on iodination give two new chloro-iodo derivatives, which from analogy with the corresponding chloro and bromo derivatives seem to be 2-chloro-5-iodo-*p*-xylene and 4-chloro-6-iodo-*m*-xylene respectively. 4-Bromo-*o*-xylene on iodination and 4-iodo-*o*-xylene on bromination gave the same bromo-iodo derivatives of *o*-xylene. Hence the compound must be 4-bromo-5-iodo-*o*-xylene. In case of *m*-xylene, 4-bromo-*m*-xylene and 4-iodo-*m*-xylene, the former by iodination and the latter by bromination gave the same bromo-iodo-derivative. The compound in question is, therefore, 4-bromo-6-iodo-*m*-xylene. In the same way 2-bromo-*p*-xylene and 2-iodo-*p*-xylene gave the same bromo-iodo-*p*-xylenes. The last compound seems to be 2-bromo-5-iodo-*p*-xylene from analogy with other halogen compounds of *p*-xylene.